

DECOMPOSITION OF HYDROGEN PEROXIDE BY HYDRATED CERIC OXIDE

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The rate of decomposition of aqueous hydrogen peroxide (0.350 to 0.022*M*) in presence of freshly precipitated ceric oxide (0.0031 to 0.0250 molar proportions) in the temperature range 25-40° has been followed by the gas collection method. The first order k_1 is steady at first, but shows a decreased value at later stages. The apparent energies of activation are low (about 12000 cal./mole). The value of k_1 falls as the oxide is gradually dehydrated by heating at a number of selected constant temperatures (complete loss of activity at about 730°).

The results have been explained on the assumption that the basic mechanism is provided by the Michaelis-Menten equation for enzymatic decompositions, but the adsorbed molecule does not decompose unless hit by another H_2O_2 molecule from the solution phase. There does not seem to be any complication due to free radical chains.

Although the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in aqueous solutions has been studied in presence of a number of metallic oxides (Fe_2O_3 , CuO , HgO , etc.), ceric oxide does not appear to have received much attention. Lemoine (*Compt. rend.*, 1916, 162, 702) reported that the oxide was a moderately good catalyst at 69.6° with 30 volumes hydrogen peroxide. In this work we have investigated the decomposition in some detail.

EXPERIMENTAL

The hydrogen peroxide was a commercial sample and contained some stabiliser. No attempt was made to purify it so that the rate of self-decomposition could be kept low. Ceric oxide was precipitated from ceric nitrate by dilute ammonium hydroxide and washed without loss of any solid. The moist oxide was kept stored under distilled water, and known weights were withdrawn after making up the mixture to a definite volume in a measuring flask. The amount of oxide was computed from the initially taken weight of ceric nitrate. It was found that if the suspensions were thoroughly shaken before withdrawal, the weight of oxide removed by means of a pipette did not vary by more than 1.2%.

Since the residual hydrogen peroxide cannot be titrated with potassium permanganate in presence of the oxide, the rate was followed by collecting the oxygen evolved in a nitrometer tube. The mixture was kept vigorously stirred on a magnetic stirrer.

Variation of Rate with Increasing Concentration of Hydrogen Peroxide

In the first series of experiments the proportion of ceric oxide (hydrated) was kept constant at 0.025 mole/litre and that of hydrogen peroxide was changed in different experiments, which were performed at 35° (thermostat 35° ± 0.1°). The initial first order k_1 's with increase in initial concentration of H_2O_2 are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
Conc. of $CeO_2 = 0.025$ mole/litre.

Initial conc.	1st order k_1 .	Remarks.
(a) 0.3500 mole/litre	0.0067	1st order reaction
(b) 0.2500	0.0129	Do
(c) 0.1750	0.0304	Do
(d) 0.0875	0.0783	Departs from 1st order at low conc.
(e) 0.0435	0.1244	Do
(f) 0.0325	0.1312	Do
(g) 0.0218	0.0967	Do

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The reaction was found to be of 1st order throughout the course of decomposition, observed only in the first three cases. The velocity constant (1st order) showed a decrease as the decomposition progressed, *i.e.*, as concentration of H_2O_2 decreased in the system. This departure set in earlier, the smaller the starting concentrations, and did so at $\log a/(a-x)=0.45$ approximately in (f), *i.e.*, at about 40% of 0.0325 molar H_2O_2 still undecomposed.

Variations of the Amount of Oxide

The above experiments do not make it clear whether a decreased absolute concentration of H_2O_2 in the system produces a departure from the 1st order reaction. The question remains open that a critical ratio of $(H_2O_2)/(CeO_2)$ may be responsible. Hence another set of experiments was performed in which the (H_2O_2) was kept constant at 0.0325M and the amount of (CeO_2) was increased from 0.00313 to 0.025 mole/litre. Whereas straight line graphs were obtained [$\log a/(a-x)$ against t] for oxide "concentrations" 0.00313 and 0.0062, the 0.025 graph showed strong departure (towards lower values of k) as the (H_2O_2) in the system decreased to about 40% of its initial value (0.013M~). The ratio $(H_2O_2)/(CeO_2)$ is about 0.55 at this point, but perhaps this might have set in even at a lower $(H_2O_2)/(CeO_2)$ ratio since the margin between 0.0062 and 0.025 for the oxide is large. An analysis of the data leading to Table I showed that in some cases a ratio as low as 0.45 produced a departure from the 1st order.

The graphs of $\log a/(a-x)$ against t , where a downward bending occurs, are typical of reactions where a 1st order eventually changes to a 2nd order. We presume therefore that the reactions are of 1st order to start with, but at lower concentrations of peroxide they change to 2nd order.

FIG. 1

Apparent Energy of Activation

Obviously in involved reactions like these, it is not possible to calculate the true energy of activation, but assuming the reactions to be of 1st order, the apparent energy has been calculated from velocity constants determined at different temperatures (25° - 40°) for two mixtures: (i) 0.0325M H_2O_2 -0.025M CeO_2 ; (ii) 0.0325M H_2O_2 -0.0125M CeO_2 . A straight line graph was obtained only in (ii) (where the proportions of oxide was less), when $\log k$ was plotted against $1/T$ and the apparent E_a was 12560 cal./mole, having quite a low value. The other graph had a larger slope at smaller $1/T$, but the mean slope was again about $1/T$, but the mean slope was again about 12000 cal./mole. It may be concluded that the reacting molecules easily acquire the necessary energy of activation.

DISCUSSION

It will appear from the above that these reactions are characterised by (i) a first order rate at a high H_2O_2/CeO_2 ratio, (ii) a tendency towards second order when the oxide is in excess, and (iii) a low energy of activation. These facts bring out a strong similarity with enzymatic decomposition, studied in detail by Michaelis and Menten (*Biochem. Z.*, 1913, 49, 333). If the peroxide= P and the catalyst= C , we may write down,

PC may be regarded as a temporary complex between the peroxide and the catalyst; the end products are of course oxygen and water, and are formed by a first order mechanism (velocity constant = k_1). PC is formed by a second order mechanism (velocity constant = k_2), but part of it may be dissociated back into P and C by a first order mechanism (velocity const. = k_{-1})

$$\frac{d(PC)}{dt} = k_2 (P) (C) - (k_{-1} + k_1) (PC) \quad \dots (i)$$

Also
$$\frac{d(O_2)}{dt} = k_1 (PC) \quad \dots (ii)$$

It will be noted that the concentration of the catalyst is not quite fixed, = $(C)_0$, but will depend on how much PC has been formed.

$$(C) = (C)_0 - (PC).$$

Hence from (i)

$$\frac{d(PC)}{dt} = k_2 \{(C)_0 - (PC)\} (P) - (k_{-1} + k_1) (PC) \quad \dots (iii)$$

since $(P) - (PC)$ is almost equal to (P) , there being far more peroxide molecules than catalyst sites. If a steady state is permitted,

$$\frac{d(PC)}{dt} = 0.$$

Hence from (iii),

$$(PC) \{k_2 (P) + k_{-1} + k_1\} = k_2 (C)_0 (P)$$

or
$$(PC) = \frac{k_2 (C)_0 (P)}{k_2 (P) + k_{-1} + k_1}$$

Substituting the values of (PC) in (ii),

$$\frac{d(O_2)}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 (C)_0 (P)}{k_2 (P) + (k_{-1} + k_1)} \quad \dots (iv)$$

Equation (iv) requires that at high concentrations of hydrogen peroxide [when $k_2 (P)$ will be large compared to $k_{-1} + k_1$], the evolution of oxygen should be of zero order with respect to concentrations of hydrogen peroxide, but at low concentrations it should be of the first order. Actually we have seen that the reaction is of the first order at high concentrations of H_2O_2 and tends to second order at lower concentrations, a $(H_2O_2)/(CeO_2)$ ratio of about 0.5 being necessary at lower concentrations of H_2O_2 with the samples of moist oxide prepared by us. At high concentrations of peroxide, the lowest concentrations reached at the end of the actual experiments are still considerable, and equation (iv) must be modified.

How are we to account for the missing order both at low and high concentrations of H_2O_2 ? It appears that the adsorption complex PC is not able to break down spontaneously into the products H_2O , O_2

The complex must be hit by another H_2O_2 from the solution phase before oxygen can appear as a gas. Hence the reaction may be written :

Such a mechanism has been previously suggested by Hinshelwood and Allen (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, 121A, 141) for the decomposition of CH_3CHO on various metal surfaces.

Since this mechanism depends on the formation of the complex PC, it is obvious that the physical conditions of the oxide may be of great significance. In the last series of experiments we subjected the moist oxide to successive desiccation at increasing temperatures. The velocity constants obtained with these dried samples showed a progressive decrease as the moisture content decreased. Up to 400° the decrease in k is not very great, but above this it is very rapid because sudden dehydration takes place near this temperature and the structure of ceric oxide changes towards fluorite structure as reported by Moosath (*J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, 2, 286). It changes to complete fluorite structure at 900° . There was a total loss of catalysis with the sample dried at 730° for 2 hours. The results are shown in Table II and the corresponding kinetic data are shown in Fig. 1.

TABLE II

	%Loss.	k_1 .	$k_{max}-k$.
A— heated at 110° to const. wt.		6066	..
B— $125^\circ/2$ hrs.	0.20	0.063	0.003
C— $175^\circ/2$	0.40	0.057	0.009
D— $225^\circ/2$	2.17	0.037	0.029
E— $430^\circ/2$	10.40	0.015	0.051
F— $530^\circ/2$	12.07	0.044	0.062.
G— $630^\circ/2$	13.09	0.0028	0.063
H— $730^\circ/2$	13.49	0.00	0.066
I— $830^\circ/2$	13.73	0.00	0.066

The graph of the 1st order k against %moisture lost (calculated on the basis of sample A) is also inserted in Fig. 1. Actually $k_{max}-k$ has been plotted against %moisture lost. Obviously there is a simple relation between $k_{max}-k_2$ and moisture lost. The graph recalls the Langmuir adsorption equation and suggests that the water molecules adsorbed in favourable positions in the oxide structure may be the seat of catalysis. Obviously the moisture is not regained by the catalysts B, C, etc., when the oxide is immersed in the reaction mixtures, or in any case it is not bound in the same manner as in A. This raises the question whether some of the bound moisture in A may not be lost as a consequence of long immersion in H_2O_2 so that the nature of the catalyst may not be quite the same throughout a single run. The slight fall eventually observed in k_1 even in the best cases may be explained in this manner. To see this point further, we allowed a freshly prepared sample of oxide to react with H_2O_2 (0.107 g. oxide to 25 c.c. of 0.0325M- H_2O_2).

till no further O_2 was evolved. The oxide was then transferred without loss to another H_2O_2 solution of the same volume and concentration. The k_1 now observed was found to be only 50% of the former.

FIG. 2

We also examined the X-ray diagrams of four of the samples recorded in Table II. We did not find any considerable change in the reflected X-ray diagram of the oxide due to heating and moisture loss. The water molecules may well be located in interstitial spaces. It appears that the adsorption complexes must also be formed through the agency of these water molecules and that hydrogen bonding or simply physical forces may be involved.

It may be further noted that the rate of stirring is of no consequence so long it is fairly vigorous. A mixture could be left unstirred during the beginning of a run, and stirred only before reading the volume of gas collected, with errors no larger than 2%. On the other hand, in the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide, catalysed by ammonium molybdate-sodium nitrate mixtures (to be communicated later), even small differences in the rate of stirring had a profound effect on the volume of gas collected. We therefore conclude that stirring in the present experiments is necessary only for releasing the supersaturation of the reaction mixture by evolved oxygen, no complications such as free radical chains being involved.

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